

Redefining the Idea of Society by its Holistic Development

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ABSTRACT: The concern about the uniformity of the population of the earth, in terms of human and fundamental rights, has become a constant concern over the past decades for the majority of politicians, particularly those from the developed countries. This reality, also known as globalization, has benefited from both sympathy and appeals. This phenomenon was taken over by Literature, Philosophy, Sociology, Theology, etc., and each field has specifically proposed different aspects of what would happen in the future. Therefore, this paper attempts to capture the phenomenon of globalization from the point of view of the holistic development of the society. The approach is critical to provoke thinking on this issue and less concluding with normative consequences. What this study adds to is that it is surprising that the approach to holistically develop the society is actually one that changes or intends to replace it. The argumentation system for this thesis is based on the evolution of some systems and the way they are used. We are talking about the theological, financial, political, psychological and social assistance system. We propose this perspective as a dialogue and as a way of directing scientific thinking to areas, considered, solved.

KEY WORDS: society, church, holistic development, virtualization, political assistance, psychological assistance, theological assistance, financial assistance, mass-media assistance, social assistance.

Introduction

The complex and holistic development of our century society must not escape the exigencies and rigor of independent judgments. Personal demand means not to say what *we* say and not to say what *everyone else* is saying, but here the researcher says what *he* wants. The multiplication of such voices can help and correct the global enthusiasm, that is heading towards “something” about which, punctually, is very little spoken. The tendency of contemporary society is not the development, but its definition and self-definition. Contemporary society does not develop, it is replaced!

In the present research, we try to provide a perspective subordinated to the honesty of what is the holistic development of the society and what would, in fact, imply such a development. The history of this century is not about the development of the society, but about its change. “Because the Creator of all made the conjugal community the beginning and foundation of human society,” the family has become “the basic and vital cell of society.”¹ Although the declaration “the family is the basic and vital cell of society” has remained, its content is long overdue. Redefining intra-family and inter-family relationships, redefining the notion of father, mother, boy, girl, etc. makes this statement even ridiculous. The longevity of undivorced families is not just exotic but disturbing. We are in another century, we are other people or, at least, we want to be other people. Reviews like: “Keeping marriage together is the will of God. On the contrary, its dissolution from human causes constitutes a grave violation of His will, which often leads to personal or collective tragedy,”² no longer represent anything normative. In the most positive situation, it can be an evocation of a classic idealism or the point of view of some that hinders social progress.

Old existential situations have “emigrated” from person towards the *communeautaire person*, then towards the *state person*, the *economic person*, the *sociological person* and, finally, towards the *virtual person*. This more or less assisted and imposed migration has come to kill the person’s personal being. We are talking today only about the personal nature of society in the trend.

Those who see the Earth as a whole give us very little real information about the changes we all share. The great international conferences of the world “should be defined as a kind of cultural councils, during which common truths should be formulated, that should be raised to norms for the existence of humanity.”³ The probability or the idea of *should*, existing in this statement have already turned into a reality. The *international* formulates common truths that *it* raises to norms for the existence of humanity. We talk about the well-being of the virtual society, while the real private or collective being retreats and is replaced. The well-being that compels us is replaced by the well-being that we create and adapt. “The well-being in the Judeo-Christian theistic ethics is not something that adapts itself to human nature, but that something to which the Creator obliges the human nature.”⁴ The society of our century proposes a relative *good* that does not compel anyone and which, under the dream of freedom, constrains us all to change us; soon we will not be *ourselves*, but we will be *others*.

The present study aims to review the problems mentioned through the perspective of the most important contemporary realities through which society develops its change. This change has redefined the past and used it as a pretext for the need to transform the contemporary society; transformation in which there is no option, only binding. Thus, we will address the holistic development of the society through the means by which it operates: virtue and virtualization of money, virtue and virtualization of social protection, virtue and virtualization of psychological assistance, virtue and virtualization of the church, virtue and virtualization of politics.

(A) Virtue and Virtualization of Money in the Holistic Development of the Society

In the postmodern society *to have* involves necessarily *to be* and *to be happy*. Nobody any longer doubts this change, made through the redefinition of *existential* common sense and replaced with *conventional* “common sense.” In Antiquity *to be* and *to be happy* meant to know how to speak. The expressed rhetoric, eloquence and

the art of grammar ensured the *to be* and *to be happy*.⁵ This reality has been metamorphosed, Camil Petrescu notes, reaching money, the only value that allows us to be and to be happy. Their distribution as needed in the global development seems to be a great achievement of humanism and the appreciation of all people, only to avoid knowing the meanings: financial values are not distributed to the needs of many, modest or poor people, but invoking their strict needs, the financial values are distributed according to the needs of those who are for good separated from reality, that is, the extremely rich. This allows a footballer to receive twenty million euros annually and a mother of seven to ten children to receive social support of several thousand euros per year.

The financial values are the virtue. Keeping closer to this virtue requires virtualization. The virtual currencies, the necessity of individual financial existence only through the bank, salary and shopping cards, etc. all imply and impose the virtualization of financial values. This reality, as if demanded by people and appropriated without any protest, clearly contributes to the holistic perspective of the new society. The antithesis remains the native perception of the situation. Sociologically it would be all about education, but it is not. At the level of the being it is the need for affections of the being; the being needs beings and less of anything else when it comes to living oneself. The infrastructure: the material needs, financial ones, etc. are just the means. "Although they are surrounded by hardships that resist educational work, much worse today, parents must form sons with confidence and courage for the core values of human life. Sons must grow up in a fairness to material goods by adopting a simple and austere lifestyle, being convinced that man has greater value through what he is than through what he has!"⁶

This statement by John Paul II radically undermines virtualization of money and virtue. He returns to the words of Jesus Christ: "*Lay not up for yourselves treasures upon earth, where moth and rust doth corrupt, and where thieves break through and steal: But lay up for yourselves treasures in heaven, where neither moth nor rust doth corrupt, and where thieves do not break through nor steal: For where your treasure is, there will your heart be also.*" (Matthew 6:19–21) This perspective is not just about salvation, but it captures

the human dimension from the perspective of its affections, the inner depths that lead it to life, to goodwill, to the collective joy, and to the futureistic projection of it and its descendants.

The virtue of money and virtualization implies two realities that disengage man from being free and transforms him into a modern slave. These two realities are: controlled money and love of money. As mentioned above, the state, the banks and some of the very wealthy people turned into a hysteria about controlling the way of each penny. This slowly mounts each living creature of this planet and configures it very strictly in terms of needs and aspirations, needs and aspirations that it will no longer be able to change. We are talking about a segregation of people based on money, a segregation first at the level of information, and then imposed. Although this phenomenon can be called development, yet it contains some things that show that it is a process of changing the society and redefining it. In such a case, people's hope is not to develop the society but to change it. Tomorrow we will exist like others, or we will not exist at all.

When it comes to love of money, the situation becomes more complex. Their virtualization is a result of the pathological love that the supervisors have over money. The holistic development of the society, which also takes into account this approach, does not mean that money, once virtualized, require virtualized security; a simple click, and ordinary people have no money left. In other words, the future society takes our safety from our hands and promises us a higher level of security in its hands. Isn't this the way to a violent modern slavery? There is a difference between wanting to be modest, resembling a life of simplicity as a virtue, and imposing a status that slowly removes you from the area of your humanity's taste in a slave robotic area. The Bible writes the following words: *"For the love of money is the root of all evil: which while some coveted after, they have erred from the faith, and pierced themselves through with many sorrows."* (1 Timothy 6:10) Probably the holistic development of the society from the money perspective should be cosmetized, should open our perspective to a person's well-being, a person who has in his own hands the safety of today and with his own hands is

planning the safety of tomorrow, a peace that begins to disappear from the people.

Misinformation must be replaced with silence. We do not need to be informed, not even correctly, about our commitment, but we must give up this violent change of society. “The meeting of the dominant economic powers to regulate the economy became global, became the field of ideological battle of the post-communist era. While, on the one hand, technology and economy are understood as a vehicle of radical human freedom, their omnipresence with its inherent norms is now alarmingly signaled as a global dictatorship and fought with anarchic anger, in which freedom of destruction presents itself as an essential element of human freedom.”⁷ Money must come out of virtue and virtualization. The holistic development of the society must leave the money on the method level, the means by which every person ensures, according to what he/she is and hopes, that he/she will go well.

In conclusion, the development of the society remains a virtue, while its redefinition can crush consciousness and being. Material possessions remain as a gift from God through which we move life and joy a day further, but by changing this paradigm, the virtualized wealth of each of us becomes the sadness and the burden through which we want tomorrow to no longer exist.

(B) Virtue and Virtualization of Social Protection

Another means by which we witness the holistic development of the society or its replacement with another society is social protection or social assistance. Man is about to become the only creature that can not sustain itself. The food is provided by others, the clothes are offered by others, the house is made by others, the children are educated by others, etc. We have ourselves, with nothing, or sometimes not even that. Social surveys decide whether I, as husband, or maybe we, as parents, can support our children, if we, as children, can support our parents, and if they find the opposite, we are robotically separated; there is no feeling, no one has rights over his being or over those that come from him. This certainty

and assurance from the outside is welcome as long as is required by those concerned, but it is slavery when coming over the people who did not seek it. It is very important to decide whether this is a development or a change of the society. Only in this case we can be correct about the projection of the future of the society and about its development or change.

Developing plenary a society means avoiding human humiliation and dismemberment. If this is ignored, we are talking about terror, we are talking about the extermination of metaphysical identity and the identity of love. We kneel the being in front “of the car”! The biblical side of social progress is entirely different. “The Church, faithful to the commandment of Christ, its founder, has always been present, through its works designed to give the man in need a material support that does not humiliate him and does not lead him to the state of the assistance, but help him get out of his precarious condition by promoting his personal dignity.”⁸ The holistic development of the society must not mean changing it but promoting it in the fundamental three-dimensional of its core: person, love, people. “Our love either creates a personality, a hypostasis, more beautiful, more vital and more durable than you and me, or it will be just barren pleasure.”⁹ Social protection and social assistance are not supposed to offering the human being to institutions that have man and family at their own discretion, but serving man and family if they ask for it. We, the *old* people, are scared of protection, we are terrified at the thought that someone rules over our homes, our feelings, the educational relations stemming from the sangvinist affiliation and the affiliation on the path of love. “The right and duty of parental education are considered essential, being related to the transmission of human life; as original and primary, compared to the educative mission of others, and this is because of the relationship of love that exists between parents and sons; as being irreplaceable and inalienable, because they can not be entirely entrusted to others or usurped by others.”¹⁰ In other words, we can not protect ourselves, putting us in danger and we can not love ourselves, hating ourselves. The corporeal lineage and the parental love began to be replaced by civilian duty. This task is very closely monitored by “the protector”¹¹ with an iron whip. No, it is

not development but the accession to the elimination of the existing society and its replacement with another. “The Bible talked about human alienation. It described two other types of alienation, and even more radical than the economic and the political ones. One is the alienation from God, our Creator, and the other is our alienation from each other, from our fellows. Nothing is more dehumanizing than the breaking of fundamental human relationships. In fact, when this happens, we become strangers in a world where we should have felt at home, and we are strangers instead of being citizens.”¹² The holistic development of society through these systems is well received and necessary in order to protect familiarity, family, decency and the ability to remain natively human.

The way we see and perceive social progress affects and deliberately changes the mentality of the new generations. They begin to have serious skirmishes about their attitude towards existence and life. These generations refuse the natural psychosomatic constitution in favor of some life’s *impossibilities* called alternative forms. “A mentality against life was born (*antilife mentality*), as is evident from many of today’s problems: let us think, for example, to a certain panic derived from ecology studies about the demographic future of mankind, which sometimes exaggerates the danger of demographic growth of humanity to the detriment of quality of life.”¹³ There is an exaggerated fear and “maturity” towards existential natural. We started to be afraid to be human, to be afraid to be men, to be afraid to be women, to be afraid to found families, and this reality allows the redefinition of man, woman, family and force, on behalf of *human rights*, that the anomalies are preferred, legalized and take the place of the natural accredited by time and God. Remaining in the original existential space and accredited by what we actually are is called *homo phobia*, and the one who gets such a nickname is marginalized, booed, and excluded.

The development of the society on social protection, mistakenly, disables man from responsibility and empowerment. Virtuality and virtualization of his protection and his well-being lead to pseudo-existence, pseudo-valorisation and pseudo-love. We can not currently estimate the good or bad of this change, but we feel it does not respond and does not fit the natural. It does not matter

if those who think like this are majority or minority, it matters that we are. We claim it to be known!

Consequently, social protection, by its very definition, must preserve our native existence. Its virtue is to keep old walls around the human community and in no case to destroy them through a post-modern *Trojan horse*. Rethinking this, the hope for the holistic development of the human community becomes real and responds to the aspirations that remain in us above the promises of Postmodernism.

(C) Virtue and Virtualization of Psychological Assistance

Another pillar of the development of the society, which recovers years of absence through an exponential multiplication, is the psychological assistance. The multiplication of the population, the problem of inter-human connections, the harmful bombardment of the movie houses, the chaos of the music being consumed, the fear of tomorrow's existence, etc. all these has brought many into a worrying mental state. The need for mental health, relational health and communitaire health is acute. The holistic development of the contemporary world can not neglect this reality. For this reason, the psychological assistance offer has grown enormously and is considered indispensable. On the other hand, the psychological assistance, although it is a very subjective branch of science, sometimes even close to occultism (see hypnosis, thoughts reading, etc.) has come from inertia or intentionally, to have absolute authority, sometimes being irreversible.¹⁴ Through this universalized branch, was forced the entrance into the family, a reality that changes the meaning: is not the family the one that gives birth to society, but this way, the society determines the family. Since the kindergarten, boys and girls have been assisted in developing in themselves the idea of not being what they are. Most parents do not know this phenomenon, nor do they estimate its effects. Psychological expertise can also decide whether a parent can still keep his children or not, or if a husband can stay with his wife or not. In other words, we have come to offer psychological assistance a segment that fundamentally

changes the order of creation, the order of existence of the human being, and it irreversibly changes it.

What is important to know and realise in this context is that no man can be absolved of moral obligations. Returning from various slippages is not done by gradually *deleting* the responsibility by a psychologist, but by constraint methods (reprehension, fines, imprisonment, etc.) or, at least it was like this so many decades ago. Only those hospitalized for aggravated dementia were exempt from this practice. The deviation from the norms of biblical ethics and accredited by the thousands of years of existence has always been reversible. The scientific segments that submit theses of another nature are not scientific, but intentional. "The Church does not dwell on proclaiming the moral norm that must lead the responsible transmission of life. The Church is not the author of this norm, nor is its judge. By listening to the truth, who is Christ, whose image is reflected in the nature and dignity of the human person, the Church interprets the moral norm and proposes it to all people of benevolence without hiding its radical requirements and the perfection of this law."¹⁵ By universalizing an authority that arbitrarily declares us fit or inappropriate, which decides against our sex or opens the way of sexes that do not exist, against the psychosomatic constitution, not only rights are offered to those who want to live otherwise, rights that we recognize, but slowly and surely alienate the human community. "So all those in society dealing with school leadership should never forget that the parents have been designated by God Himself as the first and main educators of their children and that their right is absolutely inalienable."¹⁶ From this area, the family area starts the development of the society. By exacerbating the so-called laws of the rights of man, woman and child, the innocent family, the home of the first bliss, the oasis of the first games and memories, have no right. Man became the most vulnerable and most unprotected in the place where he was once the safest.

We conclude from all this that the idea of social development should be subject to other criteria also. If the intent of the international community is to replace contemporary society, then everything is correctly done, but if the intention of the international

community is to develop the contemporary society, then certain issues need to be discussed again.

Ultimately, the virtue of psychological assistance must remain under the native authority of parental psychology, psychology that starts with the act of marriage, and complements itself by throbbing at the moment that the wife has become pregnant. And, with the birth, erupts natively and constitutively the quality of psychologist of both mother and father. No one has the right or duty to modify this divine human climate and for no reason. “The original cell of human society was represented by the family... As a result of a complex historical development guided by Divine Providence, the complication of social relations led to the emergence of the state.”¹⁷ As a result, the plenary development of the society must come from the family, not from the state, through the psychological networks of constraint and determination of the human psyche. The state is us, the families! And we, the families, are never against ourselves. The society is not disturbed by those who create illusory or concrete forms of existence, the society is disturbed by the reason of their imposition. Normality is defined by normality through itself, not by opening perspectives under syntagms: redefinition of freedom, redefinition of family, redefinition of man, redefinition of woman, etc. Paul Evdokimov noted the following: “The fools, the maniacs exist, but how sad it is to impose their vision or to present it as belonging to all mankind! The patterns of psychopathology—important in their genre—must not exceed the limits of their own world.”¹⁸

In conclusion, psychological assistance belongs first to the being we are born of, then to our being and optionally belongs to others. Disapproval of parents and being from their authoritative role of their own psychology and their own psychic by requiring the specialist, and then by imposing it, is a serious attack on the dignity of the human being and then on its freedom. Moving from the area of virtue into the area of virtualization of psychological assistance changes the society, does not develop it. Apparently it can be a matter of success. What we do not know is that man can not be changed with a man of another race or hybrid because there is no other race. This forces us to conclude that by what we do we take man out of his being.

(D) Virtue and Virtualization of the Church

One of the somewhat dilematic situations of our Europe lies in the fact that it offers a future for holistic development abdicating, in substance, the phrase “Christian Europe.” It seems, every day, that the global Christian and European Christian population is less interested in its religious dimension, especially when it comes to “civilian life,” ie the exacerbation of illicit pleasures, or new perspectives on LGBT rights. Without infringing in any way the right of everyone to choose to live as he/she wants, we ask ourselves questions about the meaning, sense and purpose of developing the society in this direction? In this equation is included the Church, an institution that in a certain way is composed of the same people. The Church, as virtue, is somehow left in our being, but as a rule is excluded. Its virtualization in the moral, behavioral, and aspirational space seems to remove it from our lives, or at least place it in a shadowy cone. The official areas of judgments and discussions do not include the church in any way, although a large number of officials belong to the church for their life as an annex. Social and individual splitting is so successful that the questioning of life in state or European institutions have, either in tone or subject, no connection with the quests, the quiet and the peace that the same people have on Sunday at church.

However, from the hierarchical areas of each Christian Church are imposed, at an informative level, quite antithetic attitudes to what is happening today in social development. This is not defining, but can not be ignored. In the context of our study, the church is very reserved, even antagonistic, with both the political element and the individuals that belong to it. Church hierarchy and militant members of Christianity see the need for the development of the society on grounds contrary to what happens in the society and in an opposite direction. In addition, the foundation of Christian teachings is frozen; in the doctrines and dogmas of the churches nothing changes.

Even if at the level of public statements we can observe some permissiveness, when it comes to formalized formulas of faith, nothing changes. “The Church strongly believes that human life, even weak and suffering, is always a wonderful gift from the God of

goodness. Against the pessimism and selfishness that shadow the world, the Church is on the side of life, knowing to discover in every human life the splendor of that *yes* and *amen* that is Christ himself. Against the *no* invading and hurting the world, the Church responds with a strong *yes*, thus defending humanity and man from all those who shake and hurt life.¹⁹ As incisive are men in their liberatinism, as docile and sensitive are in moments of spiritual research.

At the conceptual level, since the time of the Roman Empire, the spiritual dimension and the “civil” dimension were regarded as an indestructible unit. Moreover, the civil authority participates militantly in keeping the biblical Christian concept untouched. “The idea of a Christian and universal empire presupposed that the Emperor had obligations, both as a guarantor of faith and as a witness to God’s mercy towards man... The king’s vocation is to do good, and that is why he is called a *benefactor*, and when he does not succeed in doing the good, he forgets his imperial dignity.”²⁰ What has given a new meaning to the holistic development of contemporary society, development which is substituted by the rigid idea of change, is that the Absolute Good has been replaced by the relative good, the negotiable good, the created good. Most political and social decisions are taken in relation to our good, not with the Good.

This reality produces and maintains a tension at social level, between the Church and the political social element and, at individual level, between the secular tendency and the religious dimension in man. This tension is not cultivated and interested, but it is an intrinsic tension, it is a constitutive tension from the eternal and original constitution of the human being. “Man can not exist without God, or apart from God. There is no one who can do it. Through his own life, man is rooted in Him Alive... Every beating of our heart is an act of faith.”²¹ The post-modern social-political will to move the rhythm and the pleasure of existence from the constitution of creation on the desired constitution is under implementation. For this reason, the age level for taking the child out of the family for social education has dropped drastically. From seven to ten years in the sixties of last century, to three years today. In this way the child can no longer take anything from the order of creation, but only from the implemented order. We become the witnesses and promoters of changing the idea

of man into something else. For this reason Paul II declared: “The Church is called to show again to all, with the strongest and most clear conviction, its willingness to promote human life in any way and to defend it against any wickedness addressed to its being, at any stage of development.”²² From a Christian point of view, a danger is estimated, from a secular point of view, a progress is estimated, and the finality in itself is reserved for the future.

Through virtualisation of the church, a return to the frustration of communism is expected, “when the Church was forced to restrict its activity within the places of worship”²³ and, with time, their elimination. We overlook the fact that this is impossible since the people of the church form the society, that is, they express the church continuously and universally. This reality goes beyond the battlefield of ideas, ie religious ideas and secular ideas, and declares the area of struggle of existence, we exist or replace existence. The universality of the church found in all those who exist in the society is a matter that relates to the being of Christ and by His extension, to our being. “The Christological character of universality stems from the fact that the church is universal, not in its capacity as a community aiming at a certain moral perfection, but as a community that experiences and reveals the unity of all creation to such an extent that this unity is a reality in the person of Christ.”²⁴ Dialectic is not of the ideas! We are not talking about evolutionary theory and creationist theory in a room of scientific communication, but we are talking about a social experiment, we create, as in a chemistry lab, physical reactions using people. Under these circumstances, it is possible to target our own existence and what we call development to become change or even destruction. “The Church is not from this world, just as its Lord Jesus is not from this world... Its goal is not only the salvation of men in this world, but the salvation and restoration of the world itself.”²⁵

In conclusion, from the perspective of church thinking that is not intrinsic the dogma, but intrinsic the being,²⁶ holistically, it does not mean what we *do*, but what we *should do*. In this context, the church institution is likely to succumb to the holistic that involves changing the being, but the being can not cave in because it is against its condition of existence; however, it can be destroyed. Is the orientation of contemporary holistic development an orientation of destruction?

The Church is worried not about the phenomenon, but about imposing it on the family's intimacy: at the relational, educational, sentimental level and in the framing of it in society. "The rights" have violently invaded the family and the house, so the family and the house are left with no right. This determines John Paul II to declare: "If schools teach ideologies contrary to Christian faith, the family, along with other families, and if possible with family associations, must by all means and wisely help the children not to ward off from the faith. In this case the family needs special help from the spiritual shepherds who must not forget that parents have the inviolable right to entrust their sons to the ecclesial community."²⁷

(E) Virtue and Virtualization of Politics

In this historical social concern of holistic development of the society, an important and defining role has the political virtue. The ways of solving and the political proposals are so important and dictatorial, that they must be obeyed by justice, truth and life without the right to appeal. Even if they are innocent sacrifices, they must be brought.²⁸ People do not have access to this vision, and their manipulation is extremely easy, especially when the ordinary person can not aspire and create good forms, but he is the victim of the imposed good: to be able to live and have a vacation elsewhere than at home. The Church is moving hard enough to improve this situation. It "can not adopt a stable system of relations with the worldly power because the relations are always temporary."²⁹

Another issue that arises is that the holistic development of the society, although it seems an aspiration to all people, is very partisan. There are more and more political parties that out of more or less known interests deny the dimension of holistic existence of the society in favor of their orientation, not even in favor of the interests of the people they represent. Through this reality the political perspective completely dissociates from the perspective of the human being and the church that is concerned with the whole. "The role of the Church is not to divide by different political options and ideologies, but to work to preserve the unity. Even the notion

of *party* shows that it is only a part of the whole and not the whole as such, while the role of the Church is concerned not only with the part but also with the whole.”³⁰

Under these conditions, politics as an option of society has turned into a dictatorial unilateralism of interests. Voting in recent decades in very small percentages shows that society no longer wants a political system or not of this kind. However, its dictatorial ferocity can not take into account either the change or the dissolution of politics. “The totalitarian state tends to absorb the nation, the society, the family, the religious communities and even the people.”³¹ We do not see this attitude as a way in which contemporary society can develop holistically, but as one in which society is bound to be different.

All this reality leads to a phenomenon that we will develop in the next chapter: the man of our society is no longer informed or disinformed, but he is instilled another way of thinking and perception with the help of foreign and destructive information to human nature. The existential instinct of being is guided to confusion. “*Homo consumans* calls on *homo sanitas*, *homo tehnicus*, *homo scientificus*, very little on *homo religiosus* and even less *homo christianus*.”³² Solutions are offered in health, technology, and science, while they are required in spirituality, in Jesus Christ. This more or less deliberate confusion relativises the joy of existence of the being and the ecstasy of prolonging itself in history and time through procreation. “Some wonder if it is good to live or it was better not to have been born; they wonder if it is allowed to bring others to life, since they can curse their own lives in a cruel world, whose cruelty can not yet be predicted.”³³

The holistic development of the society should have the effect of reducing this feeling, this psychosomatic cry, not its multiplication. The being, without knowing and consenting, is willing to sacrifice itself in favor of those who follow it, but this is not in sight either.

Virtue and virtualization of politics has come to violently submit life. Contrar sau complementar acestei laturi a ei, tot ea luptă pentru dezvoltarea holistică a societății și, implicit, a vieții. This dilemma, this Gordian node, if it is instrumental, has no more solving from the point of view of the decisions of the society. If it is not instrumental, then there is the possibility of intimation and

self-intimation. We do not lead into mistake, but we are mistaken, we do not replace but replace ourselves, we do not constrain but constrain ourselves, we do not destroy but we destroy ourselves. The saddest thing in this phenomenon is that it sent its roots into the family. The family has grown like a pot that slowly and surely is filled with the roots of a foreign plant, roots that slowly exhaust it and remove it. This phenomenon jeopardizes both the family life and the life of the foreign plant.

The political virtue and its virtualization will end up in self-elimination; we will not be what we have been and we are what we will never be. "The society and especially the state must recognize that the family is *a society that enjoys its own and primordial right* and, therefore, in their relations with the family, are seriously bound to maintain the principle of subsidiarity. Under the force of this principle, the state can not and must not take from the families the duties that families can freely exercise alone or associated, but they must favor them positively and maximize the responsible initiative of families."³⁴ The family should not be choked by the roots of politics, but must be the root of politics. This change of optics tolerates alternatives but does not allow removal.

Consequently, the holistic development of the society must not be anchored in the political element, but the bulb of human existence, namely the family, must be found in the political element in its nativity, and this presence accentuates the aspirations for development that give us the complement of life with even more happiness. Or, such a phenomenon can not be separated from the christic dimension of being.

(F) Virtue and Virtualization of Mass-Media

The exacerbation of the so-called "right to information" has created in postmodern society the most ridiculous situation in the modern history of mankind. The words of a dignitary or of an organic law, the claim of a scientist in his branch or a gunman about his weapons can not be the object of reality in the front of the anger of press trusts or press rubbish that we consume on a daily basis. The idea of press

freedom that is multiplied by many acolytes and seekers of fame and bread can no longer be warned about truth, fairness, respect, dignity, etc. by any other authority on earth. The reaction of the population and the politics that one might forbid the press from lying or mislead or defame and discredit different personalities has become terrifying.

However, an important factor in the holistic development of the society is the media that has an almost decisive contribution. It instrumentalizes the minds and reactions of the individual and society, it imposes reactions from the political or the religious and it also processes them so that when they come to us they express what the press wishes. What the contemporaneous society has forgotten is that *not knowing* declares a superior existence with relation to *knowing wrong*—especially when this wrong is imposed as correct. “The vision of the world of a blind is poorer but not altered.”³⁵ However, it is preferable to give up intelligence, thinking and self-esteem in favor of any reality that is in trend. Man distanced from himself and became arrogant with himself. Man does not want to know but wants to be told, the man does not want to be told something, but he wants to be told, man does not want to react, but wants to hear reactions, man created a community that forced him to give up the luxury of thinking. The media make the most of this post-modern “convenience” and its success is undeniable.

These forms of information anesthetize the opinion of contemporary society and raise within it a different society. It is a society that has no inherited landmarks, but its landmarks are ahead. They wait for “parents,” “grandparents” and “great-grandparents” to be born. In other words, for those born today parents are going to be born in the future. Their real parents are just a way and a method for this generation to come into the world, but, authority over this generation, its education is at the fingertips of the “true” parents who belong to the future. The delight in such a calendar of existence has become so popular and enforced that it is very complicated to be questioned and impossible to change. How holistic this development is? “A sometimes courageous, but often hurried, search today leads to an omnipresence of sexuality. Mass media, advertising, the “revolutionary” pathos, they all broadcast a vulgarized Freudianism, in which the very meaning of death...

disappears in the paradisiacal reveries of Freudo–Marxism. The fear of “repression,” the diffuse excitation of the senses, nerves, imagination, are, apparently, linked to a whole set of deceptions.”³⁶ Any solving is followed by some unsolved realities, the latter not representing any interest due to the goal.

The information and formation of the upcoming generation has become dependent on everything that means screen. The so-called exclusion of censorship is the appearance of a violent dictatorship on the human being and a barbarous rape of human consciousness and his brain. “Television is seen as an ideal tool for shaping the subconscious, because during watching the spectrum of brain waves moves from the high frequency of the beta waves to the alpha waves, during which a huge amount of information is transmitted and written into memory. This is the best explanation for the special influence that television has on modeling the thinking and behavior of individuals.”³⁷ Besides promoting immorality directed extremely beautiful, the contemporary film industry has gone to a more violent level, the horror movies. These films are consumed, they receive very positive and artistic reviews, they are awarded in the art of cinema, etc. Victims do not matter. Ad pollution in any broadcast or movie, which in turn are also pollution, has come to express the fact that the human being represents, at the individual level, just as much as can be removed something worthwhile from it. When this becomes impossible, humanitarian calls are made for the abandoned body, in a nursing home, but dying, to get some more money.

Virtue and virtualization of the media is already a reflection of the corrupted family. The pride of not being what we are is a virtualized virtue and is the only landmark for the future generations of the European and American world in particular.

In conclusion, through the holistic development envisaged in the current historical, political and social context, it seems that society and man will be redefined. This is a violent redefinition. This happens so crowded and tough, that the native instinct of the being is no longer able to perceive it and react. If the existence of God is a myth, then this development approach will produce something desirable and destructive. If the existence of God is not a myth, then this process will produce something desirable but severely sanctioned by God.

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NOTES

- ¹ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică FAMILIARIS CONSORTIO*, November 22, 1981, <http://www.ercis.ro/magisteriu/ioanpaul2exo.asp?doc=fc>
- ² Georgios Manzaridis, *Morala creștină* (Bucharest: Bizantină Publishing, 2006), 323–324.
- ³ Joseph Ratzinger, *Europa, globalizarea și noua ordine mondială: spre o utopie a ororii? (Europe, Globalization and the New World Order: towards a Utopia of Horror?)*, in Ioan I. Ică jr., Germano Marani, eds., *Gândirea socială a Bisericii* (Sibiu: Deisis Publishing, 2002), 521.
- ⁴ Carl F. H. Henry, *Etica creștină personală* (Oradea: Cartea Creștină Publishing, 2004), 239.
- ⁵ Camil Petrescu, *Doctrina substanței, vol I*, Bucharest: Scientific and Encyclopaedic Publishing House, 1998.
- ⁶ Pope John Paul II, *Ibid.*
- ⁷ Ratzinger, 521.
- ⁸ Pope John Paul II, *Enciclica Centesimus Annus*, in Ioan I. Ică jr., Germano Marani, eds., *Gândirea socială a Bisericii* (Sibiu: Deisis Publishing, 2002), 175.
- ⁹ Paul Evdokimov, *Taina iubirii – sfințenia unirii conjugale în lumina tradiției ortodoxe* (Bucharest: Publishing House of Christiana Christian Medical Association, 1994), 138.
- ¹⁰ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ¹¹ That is the State. The state accomplishes this through social protection and monitoring systems: social welfare networks, psychology offices in most institutions etc.
- ¹² John R. W. Stott, *Noua societate a lui Dumnezeu, Societatea Misionară Română, 1987*, 63.

- ¹³ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ¹⁴ The decision whether or not to have a gun permit, driving license, the right to be a teacher etc.
- ¹⁵ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ¹⁶ Ibid.
- ¹⁷ Episcopal Jubilee Synod of the Russian Orthodox Church – Moscow, August 13–16, 2000, in Ioan I. Ică jr., Germano Marani, eds., *Gândirea socială a Bisericii* (Sibiu: Deisis Publishing, 2002), 191.
- ¹⁸ Paul Evdokimov, *Femeia și mântuirea lumii*, Bucharest, Publishing House of Christiana Christian Medical Association, 1995.
- ¹⁹ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ²⁰ John Meyendorff, *Teologia Bizantină* (Bucharest: Publishing House of the Bible and Mission Institute of the Romanian Orthodox Church, 1996), 285.
- ²¹ Oliver Clement, *Întrebări asupra omului*, (Alba-Iulia: Editor Anne Sigier, 1997), 32.
- ²² Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ²³ Dumitru Popescu, *Omul fără rădăcini* (Bucharest: Nemira Publishing, 2001), 75.
- ²⁴ Ioannis Zizioulas, *Ființa eclesială* (Bucharest: Bizantină Publishing, 1996), 179.
- ²⁵ Episcopal Jubilee Synod, 186.
- ²⁶ The Church is not the inscription, it is life, life found in just as many people as Christians. The Church is not the decree, or the synodal decision, but it is the man, the man “extracted” from Christ, and neither of us, not even the non-Christians, can have a different origin.
- ²⁷ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ²⁸ See Iraq, the former Yugoslavia, Syria, etc.
- ²⁹ Nikos A. Matsoukas, *Teologie dogmatică și simbolică, volume II* (Bucharest: Bizantină Publishing, 2006), 334.
- ³⁰ Popescu, 76.
- ³¹ Pope John Paul II, Enciclica *Centesimus annus*, 171.
- ³² Cristinel Ioja, *Homo economicus – Iisus Hristos, sensul creației și insuficiențele purului biologism* (Timișoara: Marineasa Publishing, 2010), 157.
- ³³ Pope John Paul II, *Exortăția apostolică*.
- ³⁴ Ibid.
- ³⁵ Camil Petrescu, *Doctrina substanței, vol. I* (Bucharest: Scientific and Encyclopaedic Publishing House, 1998), 250.
- ³⁶ Clement, 88.
- ³⁷ Virgiliu Gheorghe, *Efectele televiziunii asupra minții umane – și despre creșterea copiilor în ziua de azi* (Bucharest: Publishing House of the Institute of Psychosocial Research and Bioethics, 2013), 63.